

COMPREHENSIVE AYURVEDIC APPROACH TO NASAL POLYPOSIS A CASE STUDY

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Article Received on 15 April 2026,
Article Revised on 05 May 2026,
Article Published on 16 May 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20265231>

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How to cite this Article: Dr. Sukritha Y. N.*,
Dr. Syed Munawar Pasha. (2026).
Comprehensive Ayurvedic Approach To Nasal
Polyposis A Case Study. World Journal of
Pharmaceutical Research, 15(10), 1273-1278.
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ABSTRACT

Nasa is a vital part of *Pranavaha Srotas*, impacting breathing and cranial functions. *Nasarsha*, is a *Nasagata Roga*, matches nasal polyps in modern terms. Nasal polyps are swollen, non-cancerous growths in the nose or sinuses. Long-term use of certain medications can cause resistance and immunity issues. Many avoid surgery due to cost and complication fears. This study checks *Ksharakarma's* effectiveness for *Nasarsha* (nasal polyps), combining external and internal treatments. *Kshara* is a potent tool for managing *Arsha*. Apamarga *Kshara's* properties - *Lekhana*, *Tridoshaghna*, *Teekshna*, and *Ushna* - make it ideal for *Nasarsha* treatment. A combined approach with *Kshara* application and Shamana *Aushadhis* successfully managed a nasal polyp case. No recurrence during follow-up, indicating a safe and effective Ayurvedic alternative.

KEYWORDS: Nasal polyp, *Nasarsha*, *Kshara karma*, *Apamarga kshara taila*.

INTRODUCTION

Nasal polyps are inflammatory growths linked to chronic conditions, causing blockage, smell loss, and other symptoms. Prevalence is 1-4%, higher in adults over 40 with allergies or asthma. Examination shows smooth, greyish polyps, graded by size into four stages. Symptoms include nasal discharge, snoring, headache, and poor quality of life. Nasal polyps often come with chronic rhinosinusitis and impaired mucociliary clearance.

- Stage I: Limited to the extent of middle turbinate.^[2]

- Stage II: Extending beyond the limit of middle turbinate.
- Stage III: Approaching to inferior turbinate.
- Stage IV: Going up to the floor of nose.

Current treatments involve steroids, antihistamines, and FESS surgery, but recurrence is common (40-60%) and expensive. Surgery has high recurrence rates, especially in chronic cases, and adds financial strain. A safe, cost-effective alternative is needed due to limitations of modern treatments. FESS surgery is used for severe cases, but has risks and high recurrence rates. There's a growing need for an effective, affordable option beyond current treatments.

Nasarsha in *Ayurveda* is described as a fleshy mass in the nose, caused by aggravated *Kapha* and *Vata Dosha*. The condition presents with nasal obstruction, sneezing, and discharge, matching nasal polyps. *Kapha* and *Vata Dosha* imbalance leads to polyp-like growths in the nasal passage. Ayurvedic texts like *Sushruta Samhita* describe *Nasarsha* as one of 31 *Nasagata Rogas*. The *Samprapti* involves *Kapha* and *Vata* vitiating *Twak*, *Mamsa*, and *Medo Dhatu*, forming an oedematous mass.

Ayurveda's approach with *Kshara karma* and *shamana aushadis* tackles nasal polyps holistically and cost-effectively. Compared to surgery, *Ayurvedic* therapies are budget-friendly, have low recurrence, and promote mucosal healing. *Ayurveda* offers a sustainable solution for nasal polyps, addressing symptoms and root causes. *Kshara karma* and *kapha-vatahara* treatments make *Ayurveda* a comprehensive option for nasal polyps. With lifestyle guidance, Ayurvedic therapies provide long-term relief from nasal polyps.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This is a case report of 37 year old male patient who approached our Shalaky Tantra OPD, Government Ayurvedic Medical College, Bangalore, Karnataka.

CASE STUDY

Chief Complaints & Associated Complaints

A 37 year old male patient who is n/k/c/o any systemic illness was apparently normal 6 months ago. Gradually he developed nasal blockage, excessive sneezing associated with bilateral watery nasal discharge, hyponasal voice, patient was unable to concentrate on daily activities. The symptoms are worsen and frequency also increased. So, he consulted an

otorhinolaryngologist, where he was diagnosed as Right Ethmoidal Nasal Polyp Grade IV with chronic sinusitis. He was treated by antibiotics, NSAIDs and steroids nasal spray but got symptomatic relief only. Further he was advised for surgical intervention polypectomy. Patient was not willing to undergo surgical treatment. So patient opted Ayurveda and visited our OPD.

History of Past illness

Medical History – N/K/C/O Any systemic illness.

Occupationally, He works in agriculture field. No significant family history and personal history identified. His vitals were within normal limits. On general examination, there was no pallor, icterus, clubbing of nails, oedema or lymphadenopathy noted. No CNS abnormalities noted on through examination.

Nasal Examination

- Inspection – DNS towards Right side , right inferior turbinate hypertrophy
- Palpation– Examination of paranasal sinuses -tenderness present in maxillary, frontal sinus.
- Anterior Rhinoscopy– Right unilateral round, pale, glossy, polypoidal mass in the middle meatus is seen. Insensitive to probing, does not bleed on touch when examined by using Jobson horne probe.
- Posterior Rhinoscopy – Nothing specific.

Ear Examination

- Right ear -EAC clear , TM – Retracted grade 1
- Left ear -EAC clear , TM – Retracted grade 1

Throat Examination

- Posterior pharyngeal wall congested

INVESTIGATIONS

- Routine haematological investigation was carried out and findings were not of any pathological significance.
- Mobile camera image of the polyp before and after treatment were taken.

TREATMENT PROTOCOL**Table No. 1.**

Days	Name of the medicine	Dose	Time	Anupana	Duration
1 st - 3 rd day	<i>Chitraka haritaki avaleha</i>	1 tsp-0 -1 tsp	Before food	Warm water	3 days
4 th – 19 th day	<i>Apamarga kshara pratisarana (kshara application to left nasal polyp)</i>	Quantity sufficient	2 times Weekly	-	5 sittings(~18 days approximately)
20 th – 34 th day	<i>Vyoshadi vatakam+ Haridra khanda</i>	1 tsp -0-1 tsp	Before food	Warm water	15 days
20 th – 34 th day	<i>Apamarga kshara taila(pratimarsha nasya) (Nasal drops)</i>	10 drops to each nostril	Empty stomach	-	15 days

FOLLOW UP MEDICINE**Table No. 2.**

35 th – 50 th day	<i>Haridra khanda</i>	1tsp-0-1tsp	Before food	Warm water	15 Days
35 th – 50 th day	<i>Chitraka haritaki avaleha</i>	1 tsp-0 -1 tsp	Before food	Warm water	15 days

OBSERVATION AND RESULT**Table No. 3 and 4.**

	BT	1 ST FU(15 th day)	2 ND FU(30 th day)	AT(51 th day)
Polyp grading	GRADE 4	GRADE 2	GRADE 1	GRADE 0

	BT	AT
AEC	400 Cells/mm ³	365 Cells/mm ³

Mobile camera endoscopic picture taken before and after treatment. It is shown in picture.

Fig.1: Before Treatment, 1st day – Grade 4.

Fig. 2: 1ST Follow Up, 15th day-Grade 2.

**Fig. 3: 2nd Follow Up
30th day – Grade 1**

**Fig.4: After treatment
51th day-Grade 0**

The condition of the patient improved gradually. After completion of 51 days of treatment with scheduled follow up, patient has shown excellent improvement.

DISCUSSION

Kshara is an excellent *Anushastra* in the management of *Arsha*, it has *Lekhana*, *Tridoshaghna*, *Teekshna* and *Ushna* property. In *Nasarsha* the *Doshic* predominance is *Kaphapradhana Tridosha*, and *Dushya* is *Mamsa* and *Medo Dhatu*, as the *Kshara* has *Ushna Guna* and *Lekhana* property it can reduce the vitiated *doshas*. *Shirovirechana* being one of the *Shodhana karma* for the diseases of *Urdwajatru* and is the excellent doorway to Nasal passage and Paranasal sinuses which helps in evacuating the accumulated *Doshas* from the *Shiras*. Hence *Nasya* with *Apamarga Kshara Taila* for 7 days has been administered. *Apamarga Kshara Taila* is *Teekshna*, *Ushna* and has *Ksharana* property and is indicated in *Nasarshas*. *Chitraka hareetaki avaleha*, *Haridra khanda*, *vyoshadi vati* was prescribed. *Chitraka hareetaki avaleha* and *Vyoshadi vati* is prescribed to *Aincrease* the *Agni* as patient is having *Agnimandya* and is the basic factor for manifestation of any disease. *Chitraka* is also having *Kshareeya* property and is acts as remedy for *Nasarshas*. Allergy is also one of the prime cause in manifestations of nasal polyp so *haridra khanda* is given, which provides anti-allergic, anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant and immunomodulatory functions. Hence it is given as *Rasayana* to improve the immunity for this case.

CONCLUSION

Nasal polyp may be correlated with *Nasarsha* depending upon its symptoms and *Dosha Dushya Sammurchana*. In *Nasarsha*, vitiation of *Mamsa* and *Medo Dhatu* takes place. After *Kshara Karma*, *Lekhana* by *Kshara* leads to healing as well as shrinkage of mass. So, we can say *Apamarga Kshara* is effective in the treatment of nasal polyp which is cost effective also. *Nasarsha* is a chronic inflammatory disease. *Ayurveda* believes in cleansing the body and

pacifying the *Tridoshas* from the roots by using unique treatment modalities such as *Shodhana*, *Shamana* and *Rasayana Chikitsa*. The results were encouraging to start with just after the application of the *Kshara*, there was complete relief of the symptoms of Nasal Polyp. Overall, there was significant improvement of the condition. Hence there is need to implement Ayurvedic medicines in larger samples of the disease to draw a conclusion.

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